

Breakdown of the Types of Participation in Different Techniques of Comprovization on the Basis of Some Concrete Musical Examples

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***Abstract.** For a multiplicity of the author's compositions, this article illustrates how the respective generative process and the respective user interface work approximately. In addition it is discussed for which target group in the context of the daily creative practice the associated concept would be suitable and also, how an implementation with UbiMus2022 could run off.*

1. Introduction

Basically, the author was striving for several years to write generative programs for emotionally appealing music based on processing the divisors of natural numbers [Kramann 2020]. This was done in the belief that if the melodic phrases and motifs, harmonies and larger musical structures that appear there arise purely out of such a construction, i.e. not from the author's intuition and imagination, then there must be something in the numbers themselves that, when sounded out, can touch us humans. And while musical intuition and imagination can be promoted to a certain extent by musical studies, but in principle cannot be conveyed with certainty, explicitly formulable generative methods can at least be implemented as software. Whether and to what extent the musical imagination and intuition of the users of such a generative software then play a role again, depends then above all on the design of the user interface of this software, with which in one direction the parameters of the generative software can be changed and which in the other direction should provide the user with acoustic and visual feedback on the musical structure in the making.

In order to convey a first preliminary understanding of the lifeworld (see e.g. [Husserl 1970]) reference of user interfaces that is the subject of this paper, we will first mention a few examples that can be used to illustrate this particularly well. At the end of each description of a comprovization method there is a categorization concerning the user interface. A sorting is chosen that starts with concepts that require very little user interaction and ends with those where users have rather large design options.

Here, immediately the first presented concept for the algorithmic composition of augmentation canons, in which the individual voices never have common entries, is given special weight and treated in more detail in relation to the other concepts. The idea behind this is that it is precisely here that music is created that is appealing and can be interpreted very easily by laymen and, on the other hand, it is precisely here that the entire generative process and the compositional decisions to be made in it can be made explicit very well and the associated algorithm is relatively clear and transparent.

2. Composition of Augmentation Canons by Decomposition of a Large Natural Number Into its Divisors and their Subsequent Permutation in an Optimization Process

Short version: A number is decomposed into its divisors. A certain selection of these divisors is seen as frequencies of a tone sequence. This sequence of tones is rearranged until a melodious augmentation canon can be formed with it.

Figure 1. Score of a whole number augmentation canon (Score as a pdf document, see: <http://www.kramann.info/augmentation.pdf>).

For easier understanding, the result is presented here first, before the associated generative process is presented. The representation of the canon is done in only one system (Fig. 1). This is possible because a new tone event never appears in two of the four voices at the same time. The four different voices are represented by different note heads. The representation is also metric. A realization of this canon with organ sound can be heard here <https://youtu.be/J4T3gSgEHLA>.

This means that no note stems are used to represent the durations of the individual notes. Basically, only the succession, that is, the sequence of tone events is visible. This omission is intended to facilitate musical interpretation and create an openness. In particular, it is intended to make it easier for amateurs to play the piece. Two players e.g. can each take over two of the four voices and can follow when the other player has played all tones until tones of their own voice come again. While other voices play notes, the last played note of the own voice is held until a new note of the own voice appears.

Thus, instrumentation, tempo, rhythm, dynamics and articulation of the sound events are deliberately not determined by the score, but are to be freely chosen by the players. A realization of the canon in which the four voices are divided between two clarinets in B-flat and in which this freedom in the duration of the notes and when the entries occur is perceptible can be heard in this live recording: <https://youtu.be/qKNyO4E0Jmg>, adjusted score, see: <http://www.kramann.info/augmentation4to2.pdf>.

Such a tolerant and liberal attitude towards the interpretation of a piece is part of the concept of some well-known compositions of Minimal Music, such as in "*Les Mou-*

tons de Panurge” by Frederic Rzewski [Linke 1997]. Here, getting out of the process through human error is already part of the composition, making the rehearsal of the composition much easier than in those where the complexity is laid down in the score and does not arise from the interpretation:

” *Stay together as long as you can, but if you get lost, stay lost. Do not try to find your way back into the fold. Continue to follow the rules strictly.* ”

In the context of ubiquitous music, such a liberal attitude towards the interpretation of a composition, or towards the generative process, is clearly represented in [Aliel and Keller 2020]. There, moreover, a remarkable bridge is built to Heidegger’s concept of *Gelassenheit*. By no means should this concept be equated simply with carelessness or indifference. Rather, it is about letting what happens speak for itself and imposing less one’s own will on what is given, in order to gain as a profit from this a deeper insight into one’s own environment and one’s own inner relationship to it, from which in turn springs an inner calm [Heidegger 2015]. In the case of the present composition, this can then mean that the players and the listeners have more leisure to engage with and enjoy the harmony of the instruments.

In this context, it should be noted that the type of augmentation canon presented here, in which one voice never starts at the same time as another and the duration of the notes is not fixed, allows the players to stand far away from each other, because the then occurring non-negligible transit time of the sound, does not cause a problem in this concept, unlike in other compositions. As an extreme scenario, it would be possible to have this kind of polyphonic composition performed by alphorns positioned on different heights around a valley, as is the tradition in Switzerland [Jones 2010].

2.1. Idea and Implementation of Deriving an Augmentation Canon from a Single Number

The term augmentation canon is understood here to mean that all voices begin to play the same melody, but at different tempos and on different pitches. Specifically, here, in the generative program, the following is the case: The tempo of the melody of a voice i is defined as a period duration and is an integer multiple m_i of a basic period p . This principle corresponds to that which can also be found in historical works from the Renaissance for example in *l’homme armée* by *Josquin du Pres*. However, unlike in the historic ones, the use of an optimization process in this work can eliminate the need to develop and present a constructive method, such as those reconstructed here [Ott 2014].

But there are also other clear differences between these historical examples and the compositional rules as they are proposed here and as they are used in the generative process presented here. During the generative process, instead of coupling the pitches of the voices to a diatonic or the tempered scale, they are seen as multiples of a fundamental frequency f_i which is different for each voice i and which is fixed to the respective period m_i in the following way:

Let the first voice have the fundamental period m_1 and a pitch with the frequency f_k . For every other voice with the basic period m_i , the frequency f_n of the same melody tone is then $f_n = (f_k/m_i) * m_1$. This implies of course that every integer frequency of the first voice must have all base periods of the other voices as divisors. Thus, the

possible tones of the melody are initially not coupled to the tempered scale. To be more concrete, a scale of whole-numbered frequencies is used as a basis, which comprises all integer divisors of a base number b . Again, for a frequency f that is used for the melody of the first voice, it must be true that it is itself a divisor of the base number b and that all frequencies of the same melody tone for the other voices are also divisors of b . For the execution of the composition, however, all frequencies are projected onto the tempered scale. This is done by using a freely selectable multiplication factor and a transposition by a certain number of semitones. Sometimes, due to this projection it can happen that two slightly different frequencies (whole numbers) result in the same pitch in the tempered scale. Thus, the augmentation canon is only really strict if one would not play it as a projection on the tempered scale, but directly the integer frequencies. The peculiarity in the generative program referred to here is also that never two voices have a new tone event at the same time. The prerequisite for this is that the basic melody begins with a pause and also between the tone events are cleverly distributed ticks that do not represent a tone event. Therefore a list L is passed to the optimization process, which for each possible tone and prefixed to it at the beginning of the optimization there are always u pause ticks. The optimization then works by interchanges in this list L .

The goal of the optimization is also to create a cyclically playable composition despite the augmentation. The melody is therefore repeated in each voice until all voices end together. This results in: The least common multiple of all basic periods m of the voices multiplied by the length of list L gives the length of the composition in ticks.

Example: The length of L is 8 (this would be very short) $m_1 = 2$, $m_2 = 3$, $m_3 = 4$, $m_4 = 6$. Then the least common multiple and thus the length of the composition in ticks is 96 here. The melody lengths of the individual voices i would then be in ticks: $s_1 = 16$, $s_2 = 24$, $s_3 = 32$, $s_4 = 48$. In each case it is the same melody, but on a different fundamental frequency and differently stretched in time. So often then fits the melody of the respective voice in the composition: $n_1 = 6$, $n_2 = 4$, $n_3 = 3$, $n_4 = 2$.

The optimization is performed using three hierarchically considered error functions:

$error_1$ counts how many sound events occur simultaneously. $error_1$ must be zero at the end of the optimization.

$error_2$ sums up in pairs the degree of dissonance of the simultaneously sounding integer frequencies, if this exceeds a certain maximum value. The "gradus suivitatis" invented by Leonhard Euler is used for this as a measurement.

The way $error_2$ is determined is the real heart of this composition program. This part of the program replaces any classical theory for counterpoint or harmony. As mentioned before, the frequencies of the tones here are initially integers. The optimizer tries to bring integers that have many divisors in common close together and to create as large a temporal distance as possible between those where this is not the case. This view to integers corresponds to a measurement for harmonic relationship between natural numbers invented by Leonhard Euler which he called *gradus suivitatis* (see [Busch 1970]). By an additional requirement that the base number b from whose divisors the integer frequencies are taken, consists only of the small prime factors 2, 3, 5 and 7, a relative proximity of the frequencies in the sense of the *gradus suivitatis* is already ensured in principle, thus,

a preselection is made.

In addition, one could still ask at this point to what extent what results here as a musical movement satisfies classical rules in counterpoint and in harmony theory. It should be said that in the very special case here, only lateral movements occur in the voices, i.e. no parallel movements occur at all. This is the case because never two voices have a tone movement at the same time. So also for example no fifth parallels are possible.

*error*₃ sums up the intervals between the melody notes. It is taken into account whether the melodies are played by four or only two instruments.

The software of the underlying generative program is available as a processing sketch and can be downloaded for analysis purposes at the following link: <http://kramann.info/WholeNumberBasedAugmentationCanon.zip>.

In the following example a somewhat more complex interleaving of the voices with each other happens, because there the measure in which a voice sounds in a different pitch than the leading voice is no longer strictly coupled to the measure of its deceleration, but can be chosen independently of it: <https://youtu.be/zdoLYkLLd8Y> (score: http://www.kramann.info/augmentation_canon__gk_2468_6432.pdf ... a split notehead indicates that the corresponding note is altered down by half a tone).

User Interface: In principle only the large base number b whose divisors are then permuted can be specified here. This is by far the most important parameter. But of course there are some other parameters, like the base periods and the range of each voice, or the random seed value of the optimization which can also be varied and which can be found in the software in the file "parameterlist.txt" and can be changed there on a test basis. Since it is extremely difficult to find good solutions at all for melodies that work as an augmentation canon, the user is left only with amazement, or even disappointment, at the piece created after going through the optimization process.

Extent of User Interaction: Virtually none. The composition emerges from an optimization process.

Type of Use: The generative program could be analyzed and modified by software developers interested in music to produce their own works. One possible use could be to integrate the software into the chiming mechanism of a clock located in a public place, so that, for example, a new, freshly composed augmentation canon is always heard at the noon hour.

Possible Presentation at UbiMus2022: The existing Youtube video can simply be played.

2.2. Some Further Remarks on this First Contribution

Arnold Schoenberg developed twelve-tone music on the premise that the possibilities of tonal composition were exhausted on the tempered scale, and whoever wanted to go beyond that typically focused more on musical parameters other than pitch. By considering all divisors t of a whole number x , e.g. $x=2520$, and asking which subset t' of these divisors t , understood as frequency, lie within the range of a musical instrument and assigning to each of them the nearest tone m' of the tempered chromatic scale, I relate other

scales than the known scales to the tempered tuning. I get new interpretations for different parts of the chromatic scale, where again the relationship of the tones to each other is determined by the common divisors of the integer frequencies t' . This basic concept of transferring integer numbers to the pitches of the tempered scale, I have used in various ways to develop generative methods for composing.

Such a generative method transmitted as source code of a computer program enables everybody immediately to compose with it. And the explanation of the basic concept of such a generative program can at least enable people to also create variants of this generative program themselves for generating other music.

For example, the shortest generative program I have ever developed in this context works like this: Go through the natural numbers at a fixed rate and decompose each number z as follows: $z = 2^p * 3^q * 5^r * 7^s * remainder$. Whenever you then hit a number where the following points are fulfilled: ...

- $0 \leq p \leq 3, 0 \leq q \leq 2, 0 \leq r \leq 1$ and $0 \leq s \leq 1$
- $f = 2^p * 3^q * 5^r * 7^s$ understood as frequency lies in the tonal range of a musical instrument that is to be used,

... then let the musical instrument play that tone of the tempered scale which is closest to f in terms of frequency in hertz.

3. Sonification of the Menace Situation in a Game of Chess

Figure 2. Sonification of the Menace Situation in a Game of Chess.

An alternative to the preceding approach is to sonify a familiar human action. An example of this is the sonification of a chess game between John Cage and Marcel Duchamp (see Réunion from 1968: [Cross 1999]). There, the generation of the music does not presuppose any knowledge of the generative process on the part of the actors. On the one hand, this is a good thing to use in a happening, because it works without further explanation. On the other hand, however, it poses the problem that the actors are not enabled afterwards to continue this kind of practice in an understandable way. To revive this memorable concept, but in a variation, the following example did not sonify the position of the pieces as in Réunion, but how pieces menace each other on the chessboard

(Fig. 2). The distance in the direction of play between one piece and another threatened by it is taken as the cycle duration in ticks. The distance across is taken as an intervallic change from pulses already identified before. A polyrhythmic tonal mesh is created, which becomes denser and more complex the more complex the mutual threat situation on the playing field is.

To illustrate the principle, a historical game of chess was taken and sonified, with the moves being made at equidistant time intervals for lack of better information: <https://youtu.be/Zj5ws1PWLhE>.

During Damián's visit and lecture at the Brandenburg University of Applied Sciences on April 16, 2022, the game was implemented as a live performance. Unfortunately, one of the players did not agree with publishing the video with the players and so now only the recording of the desktop of the used convertible laptop is available: <https://youtu.be/Ad7sEyZNz1E>.

With this implementation, perhaps the long duration between moves might sometimes be annoying. On the one hand, this could be improved by using a chess clock and a game of blitz chess. On the other hand, however, the long periods of relative standstill also invite you to take things less seriously, walk around the room, drink coffee and enjoy the sound, the concentration of the players and the event.

User Interface: A chessboard has been implemented that recognizes the threat situation but otherwise behaves like a physical chessboard: All pieces, including those to be taken away, must be moved by the players themselves. The game can be played with a convertible laptop.

Extent of User Interaction: Chess is played by the opponents without any real attention to sounding occurring.

Type of Use: The concept is most suitable to be used at time-limited events where there is not much time to give an introduction to a tool for improvization.

Possible Presentation at UbiMus2022: A game could be played at one location. Desktop, desktop sound and possibly the camera image of the players could be streamed from this location to all participants of UbiMus2022.

4. Using an EEG Sensor to Influence Parameters of a Real-Time Generated Piece of Music with a Person's Internal Mood

Thanks to Eric Mika's hack here <http://www.frontiernerds.com/brain-hack>, I was able to use a toy brainwave sensor to modify AOG formulas and generate music with it. This is one of the first experiments with it. The electronics used provide the expression of the different frequency bands every second. It also detects whether one is more in an attentive or meditative mood. Thus, of course, no thoughts are transmitted, but rather a general state of mind: <https://youtu.be/RxvxesrQaAQ>.

User Interface: Toy EEG sensor.

Extent of User Interaction: To a limited extent, the composition can be influenced by tension and relaxation of the user. However, one cannot speak of "user" in the proper sense here, because there is no really conscious, goal-directed interaction. Rather, an inner mental state is sonified, after all.

Type of Use: The whole thing is very experimental and the usability very questionable.

Possible Presentation at UbiMus2022: The existing Youtube video can simply be played.

5. Using Knobs to Set the Parameters of a Generative Program in Individual Temporal Phases of a Composition

A "Fighter Twister" from DJTechTools is used. This device has 16 rotary controls that can be read out as midi channels and each have a value range from 0 to 127.

In an earlier version, AOG formulas were manipulated with it: <https://youtu.be/gFWBysDxcc0>

In a current version, the knobs set the cycle, phase, and value of one prime factor each. The product of the values of several knobs is then taken as the divisor of a whole constant integer consisting only of powers of the small prime factors 2,3,5 and 7. The division, if possible without a remainder, then yields a frequency in hertz. Then the midi-tone closest to this frequency is played, if it is within the range of the musical instrument being played. The controls are used overlapping for several musical instruments at the same time. This results in harmonically favorable correlations in polyphonic interplay: <https://youtu.be/VWoL-4hXbk8>.

The video below shows the act of creating a composition by reusing and slightly varying parameter sets from each section for a subsequent one: <https://youtu.be/tiTRcHpgTAs>.

User Interface: 16 knobs for changing the parameters of the generative process.

Extent of User Interaction: The user is responsible both for creating interesting-sounding individual sections, and for developing the large-scale musical form of the composition.

Mode of Use: Working with it is a bit like searching for a station with an old radio, but with the difference that quasi the current repetitive musical phrase is composed of the selection with several knobs.

Possible Presentation at UbiMus2022: As in the last given Youtube link, the handling of the composition tool can be shown live and thus a composition can be realized in real time (Comprovization).

6. Critical Afterthoughts

There are chess clubs, dance clubs, clubs where one does pottery and other creative practices, but none yet where comprovization is done as a daily creative practice (compare "little c" in [Keller et al. 2014]). To be able to offer an alternative approach to this besides a proper study of music is exactly what this formulation of explicit methods of composition that I am practicing here aims at. However, it is very difficult to motivate people to try composing in this way. Typically, once there is an event where a school class is invited, or visitors from a certain context. People come together, try something out, and leave again, without any continuity in this creative practice. How do traditions develop? How could these perhaps be implemented? - These are questions that, in my view, are currently being

asked in connection with ubiquitous music. The degree of availability of a corresponding software, the transparency of its mode of operation, and the type of user interface play a decisive role in whether the implementation of a creative practice is successful in the long term, but experience has shown that they do not seem to be sufficient by far.

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